

MULTI-MATERIALS SELECTION USING GENETIC ALGORITHM

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study is to propose a multi-material design method allowing a simultaneous selection of architectures and materials. This method deals with the association of a database of elementary architectures and a database of materials. The proposition of solutions is based on a hybrid method using genetic algorithm coupled with a backtracking algorithm. The developed method allows the definition of solutions integrating optimised physical and geometrical parameters in answer to the specifications requirements.

1 INTRODUCTION

The design of multi-material deals with discreet and continuous parameters: components, that are usually materials, or semi-products; volume fractions of the components; architecture and morphology of the components; linkage between the components, especially the nature of the interfaces and their behaviour [1–3].

Numerous studies concern the development of architected materials selection and optimisation approaches when the architecture of the multi-material is defined [4–9]. In these studies, the number of allowed combinations in the design problem is limited thanks to the uncoupled selection of architecture and material. A coupled selection of architecture and material requires specific tools able to investigate huge solutions space [10–12]. The development of analytical and numerical models is necessary for these innovative architectures equivalent properties prediction [13–16]. Moreover, architecture topological optimization is frequently required in answer to complex specifications [7,17].

The aim of this study is to propose a design method allowing a simultaneous selection of the architecture and materials of a multi-material. This method deals with the association of a database of elementary architectures and a database of materials. The evaluation of the equivalent properties of the multi-material is ensured by the use of homogenization analytical models. The search of architected solutions will be carried out by the use of a hybrid method based on the association of a genetic algorithm and a constraint programming algorithm.

2 PROPOSED METHOD

This study deals with a design problem using multi-materials including important combinatorial aspects. The selection method developed in this study is based on the simultaneous research of solutions in an architecture database and a material database. In that case, the calculation time for a complete scanning of all the combinations is excessive and requires a suitable selection tool. A genetic algorithm (GA) is used and is combined with constraint programming algorithm.

At macroscopic scale, it is supposed that multi-materials are planar and multi-layered. Elementary patterns chosen in a developed architecture database define the mesoscopic scale filling each layer of multi-materials (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Architected material design at its different scales.

2.1 Design problem

The case study concerns the design of a bilayer material for a multifunctional rectangular plate. The design objective is a 20 to 40% reduction of a reference mass fixed to 155g. A uniform heat flow (900 W.m^{-2}) is applied to the lower face of the plate. This multilayer has to satisfy several design constraints (Figure 2):

- thermal constraint: a 90°C maximal temperature is specified on the multilayer lower face;
- mechanical constraint: a $1.385 \cdot 10^8 \text{ N.m}^{-1}$ tensile stiffness is required in a plate planar direction;
- electrical constraint: a $2 \cdot 10^3 \Omega$ maximal electrical resistance is required through the multilayer width plate.

Figure 2: Design constraints of studied bilayer.

Only the thermal conduction through the thickness of the plate and the convection on its upper face are taken into account in the thermal modeling. For a flat surface, the convection coefficient h is equal to $16 \text{ W.m}^{-2}.\text{C}^{-1}$. This value is increased if the top layer of the plate consists of functional pattern (fins, pin fins).

2.2 Architecture and materials databases

In this study, an architecture database is developed using elementary patterns. These elementary patterns are chosen to be representative of the classical architectures found in multi-materials. The database can be extended with new patterns for specific cases.

The different elementary patterns are ordered as illustrated in Figure 3:

- monolithic material;
- composite material: matrix reinforced by particles, short or continuous fibers;
- cellular material like foams or honeycombs;
- functional patterns i.e. segmented morphologies that allow a fluid flow circulation.

Figure 3: Hierarchical database of elementary patterns.

These elementary patterns are associated to a material database of 67 materials including 16 metals and metallic alloys, 24 polymer materials, 10 ceramic materials and 5 natural materials. Cellular patterns including foams, honeycombs and lattice could be associated to metals and metallic alloys or polymer materials. Composite materials are defined by metallic, ceramic, natural fibres or particulates combined to polymeric, metallic or ceramic matrix. Functional patterns concern only metallic, polymeric and ceramic materials. Then monolithic patterns can be used by 55 materials. The material and architecture databases can be extended with new patterns associated to recommended materials in order to investigate specific cases.

2.3 Homogenisation models

The developed method is based on a mesoscopic scale homogenisation of the multilayer. Each pattern of the database is associated to homogenisation analytical models. The corresponding models are identified depending on constituent(s) materials(s) properties and physical or geometrical parameters. Models relevance were evaluated by the number of parameters taken into account and by the error produced in the model validity interval. The choice of the models is limited to the second order, so that the parameters only concern materials properties, volume fractions and geometry. As the method is based on a multi-scale homogenisation, a macroscopic one is made considering the stacking of equivalent plies. The solution space is too big to allow a systematic screening because of the calculation time into play imposing the use of a tool able to propose a solution in acceptable calculations times.

2.4 Genetic algorithm (GA)

GA proved to be a suitable tool to perform fast search of solutions. For example, Montemurro et al. [18] considered in their work the design of a stiffened wing-box for an aircraft structure minimizing

the structure weight. Leite et al. [9] developed a Pareto set optimization using a GA. In this case, the developed method was used to assess the interactions between a set of performance composed of mass, flexural stiffness and acoustical transmission designing a sandwich panel.

In this study, the search for solutions fulfilling the previously described specifications is made by the use of BIANCA GA [19]. Individuals of the genetic algorithm carry 26 genes which are discrete and continuous optimization parameters of the design problem. The evolution of the initial population containing randomly obtained individuals depends on crossing and mutations operations applied on genes. The GA searches an optimised individual (multilayer) which is obtained at the end of the calculation.

The algorithm efficiency depends on the genetic parameters regulation (population size, crossing probability...) which are frequently defined from an empirical approach [20]. In this study, a statistical analysis is performed in order to determine genetic parameters regulation. The effect of the choice of genetic parameters is firstly investigated on single-population mechanisms (number of generation and individuals, cross-over probability, mutation probability) and then on multi-populations (number of population, isolation time), the genetic parameters determined for this calculation are described above:

- number of populations : $N_{pop} = 2$;
- number of generations: $N_{gen} = 150$;
- number of individuals per population: $N_{ind} = 110$;
- cross-over probability: $p_{cross-over} = 0.85$;
- mutation probability: $p_{mutation} = 1/N_{ind}$;
- Isolation time: $I_{time} = 25$.

The algorithm implementation is made in FORTRAN language. In this study, the genetic algorithm is used for its explorative ability in huge solutions space. In order to perform local mapping, hybridization could be performed.

2.5 Hybridization

Hybridization allows benefiting from the addition of advantages of several heuristics or metaheuristics. The hybridization usual techniques include three methods: metaheuristics association using for example descent local search algorithm with evolutionary algorithm, parallel execution of the same metaheuristic or metaheuristic combination with exact method [21].

In previous work [6], a constraint programming algorithm (CPA) was already used to solve a multi-materials design problem, but was limited to component selection. In this study, the evolutionary algorithm is associated to constraint programming algorithm in order to perform a local mapping around the solutions that the GA identified. Among the CPA, backtracking algorithm which prove its efficiency when associated with evolutionary approach [21] was chosen and implemented in PYTHON language. These algorithms reduce significantly the calculation time limiting the number of evaluated combinations.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Individual performances are calculated according to the mass of the plate and the other functional requirements. Indeed, as the GA doesn't take into account the constraint satisfaction, it had to be included in single evaluation criteria. Thus, if one of the constraints isn't fulfilled, the performance of the individual has to be strongly lowered. In the present case study, the unsatisfaction of at least one functional constraint will result in a so important increase of the mass (penalized mass) that the considered multi-material will become automatically unsuitable. The evolution of each population according to the generation number is presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Best individual evolution of each population according to the generation evolution.

The figure 4 shows the convergence of the GA. Indeed, it can be noticed that the lowest penalized mass of both populations decreases as the number of generation increases and that the selection ends for both populations with the same individual.

Figure 5 focuses on the results obtained only from the population 1. An area of interest for the optimised solutions is defined thanks to the representation of the reference mass and the 40% lower required mass. Some of these individuals, represented by the points located above the first dashed line, don't respect the mass minimization objective.

Figure 5: Evolution of the mass of the lightest individual of the population 1

On this figure, three points corresponding to different combinations of architecture and materials (listed in Table 1) are identified. These points have different locations in the graph:

- Point 1: optimal solution proposed by GA, located below the 20-40 % optimisation area;
- Point 2: solution located in the 20-40 % optimisation area;
- Point 3: Individual disqualified because of its location outside the 20-40 % optimisation area, its mass doesn't respect the optimization objective.

It can be noticed that in all these solutions, the lower layer of the multi-materials consists in a magnesium matrix composite. These proposed solutions can be considered as relevant. Indeed, a review of recent studies dealing with magnesium matrix composites is made in Hai's work [22] showing the interest of these composites. Jiang et al. explain that particle reinforced magnesium matrix composites (PRMMCs) have a great potential to be applied in automotive and aerospace

industries because of their high specific tensile strength and modulus, as well as their high wear resistance [23].

	Architecture/Materials top layer	Architecture/Materials bottom layer	Weight (g)
Point 1	Staggered pin fins Magnesium alloy	Spherical particulate composite Magnesium alloy matrix/ SiC spherical particulate	48.31
Point 2	Staggered pin fins Aluminium alloy	Woven fibers composite Magnesium alloy matrix/ Pitch carbon fibers	115.13
Point 3	In line pin fins Magnesium alloy	Unidirectionnal fibers composite Magnesium alloy matrix/ Boron fibers	180,75

Table 1: Selected points details for constraint programming algorithm

A more accurate study is carried out on these particular points. As it was explained in paragraph 2.5, a hybridization of the GA with CPA allows an extensive analysis of the physical and geometrical parameters of the model while the architecture and the components are unchanged (Table 2).

Studied parameters with CPA around fixed architectures/materials solutions	
Top layer	Δ_t : Pin spacing in spanwise direction Δ_l : Pin spacing in streamwise direction γ : height fin/ D_{Pin} D_{Pin} : Pin diameter
Bottom layer	v_r : Volume fraction reinforcement

Table 2: Studied parameters with PCA around point 1

The results proposed by CPA around point 1 are summarized in Figure 6. For each set of parameters, this graph shows the values of the mass of the plate and the maximum temperature on the bottom face, which is the most selective constraint of this problem.

Figure 6: Proposed solutions for CPA around point 1.

It can be observed that the optimal solution proposed by the GA at point 1, corresponds to the optimal solution proposed by the CPA. For this architecture/materials association, the application of a CPA doesn't allow to propose a better solution, so the solution proposed by the GA is a local optimum of the solution space.

A complete scanning around the point 1 is performed in order to check results proposed by CPA. These results are presented in Figure 7.

Figure 7: (a) Solutions obtained by scanning around point 1 (b) Solutions comparison between solutions obtained by scanning and CPA.

It can be noticed that:

- black markers represent candidates (combination which do not respect all the constraints of the specifications);
- white markers represent solutions (combination which respect all the constraints of the specifications).

There is an exact agreement between solutions obtained by scanning and solutions obtained with CPA because the two sets of points are stacked (Figure 7-b), so the CPA is an efficient tool giving all the combinations satisfying all the constraints.

The CPA is now applied to the point 2, representing a multi-material which allows a reduction of mass but does not reach the required 40% level (Figure 8).

Figure 8: Proposed solutions for CPA around point 2.

This time, it can be observed that the CPA leads to a lighter solution than the GA. Figure 9 presents a comparison of the parameters of the two solutions. It appears that only two parameters evolved: the CPA proposed a lighter solution by increasing the pin spacing in streamwise direction on the top layer and by decreasing the composite layer thickness.

Figure 9: Parameters variations of the obtained solutions at point 2.

The PCA is finally applied to the point 3, which corresponds to a multi-material candidate whose mass is higher than the reference (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Proposed solutions for CPA around point 3.

The best solution proposed by the CPA reduces the mass of 97g in comparison with the candidate proposed by the GA. Three parameters of the initial solution evolved: the pin spacing in streamwise and spanwise direction on the top layer has increase and the fibre volume fraction composite layer has decreased.

Figure 11: Parameters variations of the obtained solutions at point 3.

It's important to note that in this case, an individual firstly removed by the GA (because it didn't fulfil the set of requirements) has been turned into a solution after the application of CPA to its physical and geometrical parameters.

Previous results are summarised (Table 3).

This result shows that although the use of GA only gave a limited number of solutions to this problem, the hybridization with constraint programming algorithm in the earlier steps of the evolution highlights more solutions with various architectures and components.

	Architecture/Materials top layer	Architecture/Materials bottom layer	GA Weight (g)	GA+CPA Weight (g)
Point 1	Staggered pin fins Magnesium alloy	Spherical particulate composite Magnesium alloy matrix/ SiC spherical particulate	48.31	48.31
Point 2	Staggered pin fins Aluminium alloy	Woven fibers composite Magnesium alloy matrix/ Pitch carbon fibers	115.13	62.52
Point 3	In line pin fins Magnesium alloy	Unidirectionnal fibers composite Magnesium alloy matrix/ Boron fibers	180.75	83.26

Table 3: Results summary

4 CONCLUSION

The aim of this work was to propose architected material solutions fulfilling several requirements. Architectures database was combined to materials databases, and associated to analytical homogenization models necessary for the calculation of the equivalent properties of the mesoscopic scale of the multilayer. The determination of solutions was based on a hybrid method using the genetic algorithm ability to investigate huge solutions space and intensifying local search on specific points thanks to constraint programming algorithm. The association of a backtracking algorithm to a genetic algorithm allowed the comparison of the proposed solution by the GA and the local solutions spaces, the improvement of a solution determined by the genetic algorithm and the creation of a solution from an individual removed by the genetic algorithm.

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